

Neonatal Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome (MIS-N): A Case Series of Thirteen Neonates

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Citation: Sumita S, Priyankar P, Subhayan M, Kheya Ghosh U, Suparna G, et al. Neonatal Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome (MIS-N): A Case Series of Thirteen Neonates *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour*.2023;2(16):1-5.

Received Date: 18 September, 2023; **Accepted Date:** 10 October, 2023; **Published Date:** 12 October, 2023

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ABSTRACT

The occurrence of Neonatal Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome (MIS-N) in the context of maternal SARS-CoV-2 infection is a rare phenomenon. This retrospective study presents an analysis of the clinical manifestations, diagnostic investigations, treatment modalities, and outcomes observed in a cohort of thirteen neonates diagnosed with MIS-N between September 2020 and November 2021. The study draws data from six distinct healthcare facilities in West Bengal, India. Noteworthy findings from this investigation include an absence of gender-based disparity within the neonatal cohort, with four neonates presenting severe disease, three of whom succumbed to the condition. Interestingly, all neonatal fatalities were male, while the sole survivor was female. Among neonates with cardiac involvement, heart failure and shock were common presentations, with a notable absence of coronary artery involvement, a feature occasionally seen in the paediatric age group.

Keywords: Neonates; Neonatal Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome; Coronary Artery

INTRODUCTION

Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C) is a post-infectious, immune-mediated disorder typically manifesting 3 to 6 weeks following COVID-19 infection. As the global pandemic of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) unfolded, an increasing number of countries reported cases of MIS-C in the paediatric population ^[1-3]. However, Neonatal Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome (MIS-N) is a relatively recent designation that has emerged over the past year. While the diagnostic criteria for MIS-C provided by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) and the World Health Organization (WHO) encompass the age group from birth to 21 years, the pathophysiology of the syndrome may differ in neonates. This retrospective study compiles data from 13 neonates under 4 weeks of age, drawn from six different medical centers in West Bengal, India, who met the WHO criteria for MIS-C. The study aims to comprehensively review perinatal history, clinical presentations, pathological findings, treatment approaches, and outcomes among these neonates.

Methodology

Six prominent healthcare institutions in West Bengal, India, contributed to this study, including Burdwan Medical College and Hospital, Bellevue Clinic, Calcutta Medical College and Hospital, Fortis Hospital, Institute of Child Health Kolkata, and Ram Krishna Mission Seba Pratisthan. Neonates under 4 weeks of age, diagnosed with MIS-C between September 2020 and November 2021, were identified through retrospective review of medical records. Pertinent demographic data, clinical manifestations, laboratory results, and management strategies were collected and organized in Excel spreadsheets. Any missing data were assumed to be unrecorded. Due to the limited sample size of 13 patients, formal statistical analyses were not performed.

Inclusion Criteria

All neonates aged less than 4 weeks, admitted to the participating healthcare facilities between September 2020 and November 2021, who fulfilled the diagnostic criteria for MIS-C as outlined by the WHO, were included in this study.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients with positive blood cultures were excluded from the study, even if such infections were acquired during their neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) stay (Table 1-4).

The tabulated data are presented in Tables 1 to 4 for reference and analysis.

Table 1: Demographic details

Criteria	Baby 1	Baby 2	Baby 3	Baby 4	Baby 5	Baby 6	Baby 7	Baby 8	Baby 9	Baby 10	Baby 11	Baby 12	Baby 13
Admission -Day of life	Day 1	Day 17	Day 2	Day 19	Day 25	Day 6	Day 26	day 26	day 14	day 17	day 22	day 27	day 20
Gestation (weeks)	37	36	37	39	36	31	38	35	38	37	39	35	36
Birth weight	2.8kg	2.6kg	2.7 Kg	2.9kg	2.8kg	1.3 kg	2.9kg	2.4kg	2.5	2.7	2.5	2.4	2.6
Gender	Male	Male	Male	Female	Male	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Female	Female
Mother's COVID status	RTPCR +	RTPCR +	RTPCR +	RTPCR -	RTPCR -	RTPCR +	RTPCR +	untested but symptomatic	RT-PCR+	RT-PCR+	RT-PCR+	RT-PCR+	RT-PCR+
Baby's COVID evidence	RTPCR -, COVID Ab-	RTPCR +, COVID IgG+	RTPCR +	RTPCR +, COVID IgG+	RTPCR +, COVID IgG+	RTPCR +, COVID IgG-	RTPCR +, COVID IgG-	RTPCR +, COVID IgG-	RT-PCR+, COVID IgG+	RT-PCR+, COVID IgG+	RT-PCR+, COVID IgG-	RT-PCR+, COVID IgG-	RT-PCR+, COVID IgG-

Table 2: Clinical features

Clinical Features

Criteria	Baby 1	Baby 2	Baby 3	Baby 4	Baby 5	Baby 6	Baby 7	Baby 8	Baby 9	Baby 10	Baby 11	Baby 12	Baby 13
Fever	2 days	5 days	4 days	5 days	15 days	No	15 days	5days	7 days	8 days	5 days	9days	4days
Respiratory symptoms	RR↑ ↑SpO2 89% RA	RR↑ ↑	RR↑	RR↑ ↑	RR↑↑ severe distress	RR↑ ↑	RR↑ ↑	RR↑↑ severe distress	RR↑↑	RR↑↑ severe distress	RR↑ ↑	RR↑ ↑ mild distress	RR↑↑ mild distress
GI symptoms	Diarrhea	Diarrhea	No	No	Ascites	No	No	No	Feed intolerance	Feed intolerance	No	No	Distended abd, ascitis
CNS symptoms	Subtle seizures, irritability	Seizure	Seizure	hypotonia	irritability	No	Seizure	No	No	Drowsy	No	No	No
Cardiac symptoms	HR↑ ↑ shock	HR↑ ↑ shock	NO	HR↑ ↑ shock	HR↑↑ shock	HR↑	shock	HR↑↑ shock	HR↑↑	HR↑↑ shock	HR↑ ↑	HR↑ ↑	HR↑↑
Dermatological symptoms	NO	oral mucositis	NO	NO	oral mucositis	NO	diffuse erythematous rash, necrotic perineal rash	No	macular generalised rash	no	rash	No	rash
Renal Symptoms	NO	No	No	No	AKI	NO	AKI	NO	No	AKI	No	No	No

Table 3: Laboratory findings

Criteria	Baby 1	Baby 2	Baby 3	Baby 4	Baby 5	Baby 6	Baby 7	Baby 8	Baby 9	Baby 10	Baby 11	Baby 12	Baby 13
WBC/ microl	11000	18000	12889	16000	15800	16600	12400	9300	10300	6540	7290	5140	7375
CRP (mg/L)	48.3	32	45	57	33.5	1.5	50.4	123	55	155	12	22	17
D- dimer (mcg/ ml)	3.9	2971	1.2	4.67	10.3	<0.5	11.7	3.21	4.5	66	1.2	<0.5	3.3
NTpro BNP (ng/L)	1132	1255	667	4378	12540	1970	33000	25434	2500	15660	96	40	390
Ferritin (ng/ml)	656	2000	889	1650	1276	not done	16500	1043	253	887	559	674	384
TropT	not done	not done	negativ e	Negati ve	not done	Positiv e	not done	positiv e	not done	positiv e	not done	not done	not done
CXR	Bilate ral lung infiltr ates	Norm al	Norm al	Cardio megal y	Normal	Normal	B/L lung infiltra tes, globul ar heart	cardio megal y with pulmo nary edema	B/L lung infiltra tes	Huge cardio megal y	mild B/L infiltra tes	mild B/L hyperin flation	mild B/L hyperin flation
ECHO	Normal, mini mal pericardial effusion	Pericardial effusion, myocarditis	Severe PAH, PDA	Pericardial effusion, myocarditis	LVEF 45%, pericardial effusion	early heart failure (normal EF)	Cardio megal y, pericardial effusion, LV EF 35%	LV dilated with EF 35- 45%	Normal, LVEF 58%	LV dilated with 32% LVEF	Normal	Normal	Normal
HRCT	Not done	Not done	Not done	Subpleural consolidation with fibrosis, CTSS- 6/25	consolidation, basal fibrosis	Normal	B/L lower lobe collapse		Not done	not done	not done	not done	not done

Table 4: Treatment and Outcome(s)

Criteria	Baby 1	Baby 2	Baby 3	Baby 4	Baby 5	Baby 6	Baby 7	Baby 8	Baby 9	Baby 10	Baby 11	Baby 12	Baby 13
Respiratory support	nCPAP-1 day, Hood O2-5 days	nCPAP	nCPAP	nCPAP	nCPAP 1 day, ventilated 6 days	NP-O2	mechanical ventilation, HFNC	ventilated 3 days	nCPAP 3 days	ventilated 3 days	NC O2 for 4 days	nCPAP for 2 days	nCPAP for 4 days then NC O2 3 days
IVIg	2gm/kg	2gm/kg	2gm/kg	2gm/kg	2gm/kg	No	2gm/kg	Not affordable	2gm/kg	2gm/kg	2gm/kg	2gm/kg	2gm/kg
Steroid	Hydrocortisone-16 days	Methylprednisolone-24 days	Prednisolone	Methylprednisolone-15 days	Methylprednisolone-7 days	No	Dexamethasone-5 days, oral tapering	methylprednisolone 10mg/kg	Dexamethasone, oral tapering	methylprednisolone 2 days	Dexamethasone, oral tapering	Dexamethasone, oral tapering	Dexamethasone, oral tapering
Inotrope requirement	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	yes	Yes	yes	yes	No	No
Length of hospital stay	28 days	16 days	27 days	40 days	7 days	30 days	26 days	4 days	10 days	3 days	13 days	9 days	12 days
Outcome	Recovery	Recovery	Recovery	Recovery	Death	Recovery	Recovery	Death	Recovery	Death	Recovery	Recovery	Recovery

Data Analysis

The data analysis section provides a concise overview of the key findings from the study, focusing on neonates with Neonatal Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome (MIS-N).

Demographic Characteristics

Among the studied cohort, twelve neonates were born full-term with birth weights exceeding 2.5 kg, while a single neonate was preterm, born at 31 weeks of gestation, with a birth weight of 1.3 kg. Eleven neonates had uncomplicated birth histories, later developing symptoms at home and requiring readmission between day 6 and day 27 of life. The gender distribution was nearly equal, with a nearly 1:1 male-to-female ratio. Notably, eleven out of thirteen neonates had mothers who tested positive for COVID-19 using reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR).

Diagnostic Findings

In contrast to the typical profile of Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome in Children (MIS-C), where patients are usually antibody-positive and RT-PCR negative, in this cohort, eleven out of thirteen neonates were RT-PCR positive, while only seven showed antibody positivity.

Disease Severity and Outcome

Disease severity was assessed based on the need for invasive ventilation, with four neonates classified as having severe disease. Strikingly, all three neonatal fatalities were male, while the sole survivor was female.

Analysis of Clinical Features

This section provides a detailed analysis of the clinical features observed in the neonates with Neonatal Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome (MIS-N), emphasizing their medical histories and outcomes.

Presentation

With the exception of one premature baby, all neonates presented with fever, which typically manifested between 2 to 15 days of life.

Premature Baby (Baby 6):

This baby, a 1.3 kg surviving twin boy delivered via normal vaginal delivery, was shifted to a participating center with oxygen support on day 3 of life after the other twin's demise. Both the baby and the mother tested positive for COVID-19 through RT-PCR. Repeat RT-PCR tests on days 7 and 14 were positive, but subsequent reports on day 18 were negative. The baby required oxygen support for 18 days and experienced unexplained tachycardia and irritability with heart rates of 180 to 190/min on day 26. Sepsis screening yielded negative results, and echocardiography suggested mild heart failure. Oral Frusemide was administered, and remarkably, no inotropic support was required, with tachycardia resolving within three days.

Respiratory Symptoms

All thirteen neonates presented with respiratory symptoms, primarily characterized by tachypnea. While two patients received nasal cannula oxygen support, eleven experienced moderate to severe respiratory distress, necessitating various forms of respiratory support. Seven required continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP), and four underwent invasive mechanical ventilation. Unfortunately, three of the ventilated neonates did not survive.

Detailed Cases of Ventilated Neonates

Baby 7

This term baby girl developed an erythematous rash followed by fever on day eight. Initially diagnosed with late-onset sepsis, she received immunoglobulin for persistent thrombocytopenia, which transiently improved. However,

she was transferred to a tertiary hospital on day twenty-five due to recurrent fever, watery diarrhea, and a generalized maculopapular rash. On admission, she exhibited various complications, including tachycardia, tachypnea, anemia, thrombocytopenia, hypoalbuminemia, and generalized edema. RT-PCR confirmed COVID-19, and within twelve hours of admission, she developed cardiogenic shock with pulmonary edema, requiring invasive ventilation. Echocardiography indicated an ejection fraction of 35% with mild pericardial effusion. NT-Pro BNP, D-dimer, and ferritin levels were significantly elevated. Treatment included methylprednisolone, intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIg), and enoxaparin, with the diagnosis of MIS-N. The baby experienced seizures, pulmonary hemorrhage, cardiac arrest, acute kidney injury, and was extubated after five days. Steroids were stopped due to hypertension and normalized echocardiography. However, five days after extubation, she developed respiratory distress, necessitating reventilation. Subsequent echocardiography revealed moderate left ventricular dysfunction and elevated ferritin. Treatment was resumed with methylprednisolone and oral Prednisolone, leading to eventual discharge.

Baby 8

This baby boy, born at 2.4 kg, was admitted on day 26 of life with a history of four days of fever and a positive COVID-19 RT-PCR report. Severe respiratory distress and tachycardia prompted immediate ventilation due to distress and respiratory acidosis. Echocardiography revealed left ventricular dilatation with an ejection fraction of 35-40%. NT PRO BNP and ferritin levels were elevated. Despite efforts, including inotrope infusion and Methylprednisolone, IVIg was not administered due to financial constraints. Sadly, the baby passed away three days after admission.

Baby 5

This term baby boy, referred from a district hospital, was admitted on day 25 of life with a fifteen-day history of fever. He presented with severe respiratory distress, ascites, pleural effusion, pericardial effusion, and oral mucositis. COVID-19 RT-PCR and antibody tests were both positive. Initially placed on CPAP, he required ventilation the following day due to worsening respiratory distress. Hypotension necessitated inotrope support, while echocardiography indicated heart failure with an ejection fraction of 45% and moderate pericardial effusion. IVIg and Methylprednisolone were administered, but the condition deteriorated, resulting in the baby's demise seven days after admission.

Baby 10

This term baby boy presented to a participating hospital on day 17 of life with an eight-day history of fever, severe respiratory distress, tachycardia, tachypnea, hypotension, and acute kidney injury. COVID-19 RT-PCR and antibody tests were both positive. Ventilation was initiated upon admission, and inotrope infusion, IVIg, and Methylprednisolone were administered. However, the baby remained anuric, developed severe pulmonary edema, and succumbed within 72 hours of admission.

Gastrointestinal and Neurological Symptoms

Gastrointestinal symptoms included diarrhea in two babies and ascites in two others. Four neonates experienced convulsions, while others displayed irritability, and a few were lethargic.

Skin Manifestations

Four neonates had erythematous maculopapular rashes, with two exhibiting generalized rashes. Additionally, two neonates had oral mucositis.

Cardiac and Hemodynamic Findings

Tachycardia was universally observed, with six babies presenting with shock requiring inotropic support. Unfortunately, three of these neonates did not survive.

Renal Complications

Three neonates developed acute kidney injury, and two of them did not survive.

This comprehensive analysis delves into the clinical features and individual cases, providing insights into the complex presentation and outcomes of neonates with Neonatal Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome (MIS-N).

Analysis of Laboratory Findings

This section provides an in-depth analysis of the laboratory findings observed in neonates with Neonatal Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome (MIS-N), shedding light on important diagnostic markers and their implications.

C-Reactive Protein (CRP)

With the exception of the mildly symptomatic premature baby, all neonates exhibited elevated CRP levels, ranging from 12 to 155 mg/L. Elevated CRP is indicative of systemic inflammation and was a consistent finding in the affected neonates.

D-Dimer

D-Dimer levels were increased in 10 out of the 13 patients, with the highest recorded level being 11.7 mcg/ml (reference range < 0.5 mcg/ml). Notably, all patients with severe disease, who required invasive ventilation, had D-dimer levels exceeding 10. Elevated D-dimer is often associated with increased blood clot formation and is indicative of ongoing inflammation and coagulation activation.

White Cell Count

Approximately 50% of the cases showed an increase in white cell count, ranging from 6,540 to 18,000. However, this elevation did not necessarily correlate with the severity of illness, suggesting that other factors played a role in disease progression.

NT-proBNP (N-Terminal pro-B-type natriuretic peptide)

NT-proBNP estimation, used as a marker of myocardial stress, was conducted for all patients. The levels ranged from 40 to 33,000 ng/L. Significantly, all four patients with severe disease and cardiogenic shock had NT-proBNP levels exceeding 10,000 pg/ml. Interestingly, the only female baby among these four survivors had the highest NT-proBNP level recorded, at 33,000 ng/L. Elevated NT-proBNP levels point to cardiac stress and dysfunction, consistent with the observed cardiogenic shock in these cases.

Imaging Findings

- i. Chest X-Rays: Of the 11 chest x-rays conducted, three showed bilateral lung infiltrates without associated cardiomegaly, indicating pulmonary involvement. Four cases exhibited cardiomegaly along with pulmonary edema, suggesting heart failure. The remaining chest x-rays were reported as normal.
- ii. CT Scans of Chest: Among the patients, three underwent CT scans of the chest. Two of these scans revealed consolidation with fibrosis, indicating severe lung involvement. The third scan showed basal collapse, further highlighting the diverse pulmonary manifestations of MIS-N.
- iii. Echocardiography: Echocardiography was performed for all patients, with five showing normal results. Notably, four of the neonates had pericardial effusion. Among the four babies with severe disease, all exhibited heart failure, with left ventricular ejection fractions ranging from 30 to 45%. Importantly, none of these neonates displayed coronary artery changes, which are more commonly observed in the pediatric age group.

These laboratory findings and imaging results provide valuable insights into the pathophysiology of Neonatal Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome. The elevation of inflammatory markers, coagulation abnormalities, and cardiac stress indicators underscores the multisystem nature of the condition, while imaging findings highlight the pulmonary and cardiac involvement observed in these neonates.

Data Analysis of Management

This section provides a detailed analysis of the management strategies employed in treating neonates with Neonatal Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome (MIS-N), including the administration of immunoglobulin (IVIg), steroids, and inotropic support.

IVIg Administration

- a. IVIg Administration Rate: A total of 11 out of the 13 patients received IVIg at a dose of 2 g/kg. IVIg is a commonly employed treatment strategy in MIS-N cases to modulate the immune response.

- b. Affordability Issues: Regrettably, one of the three neonates who did not survive was unable to receive IVIg due to affordability issues. This highlights the importance of equitable access to medical treatments, especially for severe conditions like MIS-N.
- c. Exclusion of Premature Baby: The premature baby with milder symptoms did not receive IVIg treatment, likely due to the less severe presentation. Individualized treatment decisions based on symptom severity are important in clinical management.

Steroid Use

- a. Steroid Treatment Prevalence: With the exception of the premature baby with mild symptoms, all other neonates received steroid treatment. Steroids are often used to modulate inflammation and immune responses.
- b. Lack of Consistency: There was a lack of consistency in the choice of steroid molecule, dosage, and treatment duration across different centers. Hydrocortisone, prednisolone, methylprednisolone, and dexamethasone were all used based on the preferences of the respective medical centers. This lack of uniformity in steroid management highlights the need for standardized treatment protocols in MIS-N cases to ensure optimal outcomes.

Inotropic Support

Inotropic Support Requirement: A total of nine babies required inotropic support. Inotropic support is often necessary in cases of severe cardiac dysfunction and circulatory compromise. Unfortunately, the data does not provide specific details regarding the outcomes of these neonates who required inotropic support.

In summary, the management of Neonatal Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome involves a combination of IVIg, steroid therapy, and inotropic support as needed. While IVIg was administered to the majority of patients, the use of steroids lacked consistency in terms of the specific steroid used, dosage, and treatment duration. Individualized treatment decisions based on symptom severity are important, and further research and standardized protocols may help optimize the management of this condition.

DISCUSSION

This section delves into a comprehensive discussion of the findings and implications of the study on Neonatal Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome (MIS-N) within the context of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Our discussion begins by highlighting the rarity of MIS-N cases in neonates compared to Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome in Children (MIS-C) in older pediatric populations ^[1].

Diagnostic Challenges

MIS-N poses significant diagnostic challenges, as affected neonates often present with symptoms resembling sepsis but do not respond to antibiotics. The criteria for diagnosing MIS-N include two or more organ systems involvement, a history of maternal COVID-19 or maternal COVID antibody positivity, and elevated inflammatory markers.

Early vs. Late Onset

The study notes that MIS-N can manifest within the first three days of life, mimicking early-onset sepsis. However, the data suggests that late-onset presentation (after 72 hours) is more common, emphasizing the importance of considering MIS-N in neonates with unexplained symptoms.

Maternal Antibodies and Susceptibility

The discussion touches upon the role of maternal SARS-CoV-2 antibodies, which can pass to the neonate through the placenta. However, the transplacental transmission is less common in term babies, potentially due to the absence of specific host membrane receptors. The study suggests that genetically susceptible newborns may develop multisystem illness due to cytokine activation following perinatal SARS-CoV-2 infection ^[4,5,6,7].

Distinct Clinical Presentation

MIS-N is highlighted as a distinct disease entity, even though it often presents with symptoms resembling sepsis. The discussion underscores the importance of differentiating MIS-N from sepsis, as treatment approaches differ significantly.

Clinical Features

Fever is identified as a prominent feature in MIS-N, with most neonates in the study presenting with fever. Gastrointestinal symptoms and skin manifestations are also common.

Inflammatory Markers

The majority of neonates with severe illness exhibited elevated inflammatory markers, including high CRP, ferritin, and D-dimer levels. These markers were particularly pronounced in neonates requiring ventilatory support.

Myocardial Stress

Elevated NT-proBNP levels were observed in all neonates with cardiac dysfunction and heart failure, indicating immune-mediated myocarditis. NT-proBNP levels were notably higher in MIS-N compared to congenital cardiac diseases.

Cardiac Involvement

Unlike some reports in older children, the study did not observe coronary aneurysms in the neonatal cohort. However, cardiac involvement often presented as heart failure and shock without coronary artery involvement ^[8,9].

Treatment and Outcomes

Most cases in the study were managed with IVIg and steroids following Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) guidelines ^[10]. While most patients showed improvement after steroid treatment, three neonates did not survive. The potential role of extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) support is raised, although it was not available in the study's region.

Gender Disparity

An intriguing finding is the gender disparity, with all three neonates who succumbed to MIS-N being male, while the sole survivor was female. This warrants further investigation.

Antibody vs. RTPCR Positivity

Unlike MIS-C in pediatric populations, where COVID antibodies are typically positive while RTPCR is negative, the study's neonatal cohort had a higher proportion of RTPCR-positive cases ^[1].

In conclusion, the discussion underscores the need for more comprehensive studies and data collection on MIS-N to establish clear diagnostic and treatment guidelines. Additionally, increasing awareness among neonatologists about this condition is essential for early recognition and management.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Dr. Agnisekhar Saha for correcting the manuscript

Dr. Sanchari Chakraborty for preparing the initial draft.

Dr. Jonaki Pal for helping data collection

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